

Inaccurate fossil placement does not compromise tip-dated divergence times

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Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: Empirical distributions of the proportion of missing data across extant and fossil taxa. Data was gathered from the same 12 empirical datasets employed to validate other aspects of the evolutionary simulations. See matrix-level distributions of missing data in Fig. S2.

Figure S2: Average amounts of missing data across empirical (red) and simulated (yellow) datasets. Axes correspond to the mean fraction of missing data per terminal, for both fossil and extant terminals (see taxon level distributions of missing data in Fig. S1). Dotted lines mark the location of the centroid for empirical datasets. The three empirical datasets shown with empty circles contained exclusively fossil terminals, and their location on the y-axis is therefore fixed to the mean of the remaining datasets. Over 98% of simulated datasets fall within the convex hull determined by empirical datasets, with only a handful of matrices showing excessively low/high amounts of missing data among fossil terminals.

Figure S3: Empirical (grey bars) and fitted (red line) distributions of fossil longevities in millions of years (Ma). Empirical data corresponds to the entire Paleobiology Database (PBDB, <https://paleobiodb.org/>), truncated to a maximum longevity of 100 Ma. Fitted line corresponds to an exponential distribution, with an offset of 0.0117 Ma (minimum value observed in the data). Mean longevity of both distributions is 8.67 Ma.

Figure S4: Alternative prior probabilities used to constrain the root age of the FBD analyses, exemplified with a dataset whose earliest fossil representative had an older bound at 199.13 Ma. Uniform prior (red) were designed to span a time frame extending 107.7 Myr into the past, while exponential priors (grey) contained 95% prior density within that same interval, but had a soft maximum bound that allowed for much older ages. Nonetheless, the mean values of exponential priors (grey circle) were always closer to the true age (yellow circle) than those of uniform priors (red circle)

Figure S5: Average error in absolute node age estimates obtained under the joint prior. Similar patterns of systematic bias to those obtained in the full analyses (shown in Figs. 2D and S7D) can be observed, including a convex relationship between temporal bias and node depth, and a tendency to overestimate the age of young and old nodes, and underestimate those of all others. However, note that the absolute node age error of nodes closest to the root of the tree is much smaller than in the analyses with morphological data.

Figure S6: Examples of mismatches between inferred (left) and true (right) extant subtrees. One simulation per level of fossil sampling was selected at random, and a consensus extant subtree was built using median ages among posterior topologies. Branches are colour coded based on the level of over/underestimation of their lengths. The common temporal axis displays time since the origin, and has tick marks separated by 50 Ma. Excessively old ages for deep nodes are mostly obtained through the stretching of long branches connecting the clades originating from the deep ancient radiation, a pattern common to all levels of fossil sampling.

Figure S7: Determinants of accuracy in fossil placement and node age estimates. The variables depicted are equivalent to those of Fig. 1, but results correspond to analysis under a uniform root age prior. **A.** The frequency of correct fossil placement for various relative ages and proportions of missing data. **B.** Average magnitude of the absolute error in age estimates for nodes at different depths. **C.** Proportions of nodes with true ages outside the 95% HPD. **D.** Average error in absolute node age estimates. Values correspond to those shown in **B**, but averaged without removing the sign of the deviation, showing systematic biases in the direction of the estimation error. Circles denote the mean difference between true ages and median posterior estimates, error bars show the average width of the 95% HPD. **E.** Relative error in age estimates for nodes at different depths. Values were computed as in **D**, but error was standardised by dividing by the true ages.

Figure S8: Comparison of node age coverage (i.e., fraction of true ages contained within 95% HPD inference intervals) for analyses run under uniform and offset exponential priors for the age of the root. For each analysis, coverage was estimated after binning true node ages into 10 intervals spanning the distance between root and tips (labelled as 0 and 9, respectively; see inset), and values averaged across all analyses. The dashed line shows equal coverage across both conditions. The largest deviation occurs for the oldest nodes, for which analyses under a uniform root age prior show lower coverage.

Figure S9: Increased fossil sampling results in higher topological accuracy (i.e., increased probability of inferring the correct position of fossil terminals [A], decreased distance between true and inferred positions [C]; see also Fig. S10) and higher temporal accuracy (increased proportion of true node ages contained within 95% HPDs [B], decreased error in node age estimates [D]). Results correspond to offset exponential distributions to model the root age prior, but results are identical under uniform priors.

Figure S10: The average length of branches in the extant subtree increases as fossils represent a larger fraction of sampled terminals. This, plus the overall fewer number of branches in the extant subtree, likely drive the higher topological accuracy seen as more fossils are sampled (see Figs. 2 and S9). Branch lengths were standardised by the root-to-tip distance.

Figure S11: Higher topological accuracy does not translate into higher temporal accuracy. The variables depicted are equivalent to those of Fig. 2, but results correspond to analysis under a uniform root age prior. Top and bottom graphs show alternative proxies to estimate the success in inferring overall fossil placement and divergence times. Relationships between these variables are never positive, as expected under the null hypothesis (see Fig. 2). Trend lines were fitted using general additive models, and are shown for visualisation purposes only; ρ and P values correspond to Spearman's rank correlations. The addition of topological accuracy to the generalised linear models increased R^2 values from 0.271-0.316 to 0.301-0.318, relative to models including only the level of fossil sampling as predictor.